

After-sales services of home appliances - evidence from Sri Lanka

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Abstract

The provision of after-sales services is considered as a source of product differentiation leading to competitive advantage of a firm. As a consequence, there is a need of monitoring and measuring the activities of after-sales service departments to ensure that the objectives of their existence are satisfied. Yet, it is very rare to find previous studies that investigated after-sales service provision. We investigated different dimensions of after-sales service provision of home appliances in the Sri Lankan context. The study operationalized different dimensions of after-sales service provision from three different perspectives and used multiple parameters to evaluate the nature of provision.

Key words: after-sales services, after-sales service department, after-sales service personnel, Sri Lanka

Introduction

In the present day, the retailers of home appliances do not consider their active role end with an actual sale of a product (Levitt, 1983); they provide a set of supporting after-sales services to customers. After-sales services include support services that are provided to the customer after the product has been sold and delivered such as technical advice for use, maintenance, and the provision of spare parts and repair services (Low, 2013; Saccani et al., 2007; Vitasek, 2006) to ensure a trouble-free use over the useful lifespan of the appliance (Loomba, 1998; Rigopoulou et al., 2008).

Previous research identifies after-sales services as a part of customer relationship management (Ramaswamy et al., 2002; Shaharudin et al., 2009; Vitasek, 2006) leading to increased customer loyalty and brand reputation (Saccani et al., 2006; Shaharudin et al.,

2009). According to some previous research (such as Alexander et al., 2002; Wise and Baumgartner, 1999), profit margin that can be generated with the provision of after-sales services is higher compared to a product sale without it. Hence, the provision of after-sales services is considered as a source of product differentiation leading to competitive advantage of a firm (Levitt, 1983; Low, 2013; Mathe and Shapiro, 1990; Ramaswamy et al., 2002). Due to this emergent importance of the provision of after-sales services, there is a trend of after-sales service departments to evolve as a strategic driver ensuring increased customer satisfaction, retention, and market growth (Cavalieri et al., 2007). As a consequence, there is a need of monitoring and measuring the activities of after-sales service departments to ensure that the objectives of their existence are satisfied. However, our review of publications in leading databases (such as EbscoHost, Taylor and Fancies, Sage, Wiley and Emerald) suggests that it is very rare to find previous studies that investigated the provision of after-sales services. The few available empirical studies (such as Cavalieri et al., 2007; Rigopoulou et al., 2008; Saccani et al., 2006; Shaharudin et al., 2009), conceptual papers (such as Choudhary et al., 2011) and practitioner viewpoints (such as Lele, 1997) imply the need of monitoring activities of the provision of after-sales services.

In the above context, the purpose of our study was to investigate different dimensions of the provision of after-sales services of home appliances. Our study is unique in the design as it collected data from multiple sources, i.e., service engineers, service technicians and customers whereas previous studies relied on a single source for data. For instance, Raychaudhuri and Farooqi (2013) and Shaharudin et al. (2009) used data provided by customers while Saccani et al. (2006) used data provided by managers.

Consistent with the objectives, in the next section the literature on the provision of after-sales services is reviewed in brief. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a

discussion on the managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Review of literature

Customer satisfaction is the key in the provision of after-sales services (Ramaswamy et al., 2002) since customer satisfaction leads to increased customer loyalty, brand reputation and ultimately increased revenue for the firm (Levitt, 1983). Although we were unable to find comprehensive studies that investigated several dimensions of after-sales services in a single study, we were able to find few studies (such as Choudhary et al., 2011; Raychaudhuri and Farooqi, 2013; Shaharudin et al., 2009) that investigated certain dimensions of after-sales services. The findings of these studies are reviewed in brief in the following paragraphs.

Previous studies (e.g., Cohen et al., 2006) identified the importance of having a well-defined organizational structure with decision-making authority to provide prompt services to customers. Further, previous studies (e.g., Atkinson, 2012; Cohen et al., 2006) identified the importance of having an effective material movement monitoring system to avoid unnecessary delays in the delivery of materials/parts to comply with timely delivery of the repaired product/replacement to the customer. Furthermore, the need of effective documenting and record keeping practices were identified (Dagger and Sweeney, 2007) as important since documenting and record keeping provide key information such as the history of repairs/replacements for a product, the recurrence of faults, and actions taken to avoid such recurrences.

Previous research also identified warranty as a key dimension of after-sales services (such as Shaharudin et al., 2009; Murthy, 2004; Raychaudhuri and Farooqi 2013). Warranty provides assurance of quality of the purchased product, where longer warranty period assures a higher quality and reliability (Murthy, 2004; Raychaudhuri and Farooqi, 2013; Shaharudin

et al., 2009; Udell and Anderson, 1968). Previous studies (e.g., Choudhary et al., 2011) also suggest the need of having a clear charging procedure for services provided beyond the warranty period, which will minimise misunderstanding and any conflicts between the after-sales department and customer.

Most importantly, previous studies suggest the importance of having an appropriate complaint procedure for customers (Terentis et al., 2002). Call centres are increasingly becoming customers' first point of contact for the registration of complaints/faults of a product playing a key role as a middleman between customers and the after-sales service department (Jaiswal, 2008). These call centres use human agents or automatic voice response machines to communicate with customers (Moon et al., 2004). Call centre's manner in handling customer concerns and the assurance of timely solutions were identified as important contributors to customer satisfaction (Jaiswal, 2008). Yet, previous research (e.g., Jaiswal, 2008, Terentis et al., 2002) suggests that many call centres failed to contribute in achieving customer satisfaction due to ignoring softer dimensions such as empathy and assurance in dealing with customers. The outcomes of after-sales services reflect accomplishments as a result of the service provision (Brush and Artz 1999). According to Brush and Artz (1999), outcomes are necessarily time oriented; outcomes are affected by capacity and competence of the after-sales service department to diagnose faults at a minimum time, and availability of resources to address such faults or provide a replacement successfully. In this regard, previous studies (e.g., Atkinson, 2012; Cohen et al., 2006; Lervik et al., 2010; Mathe and Shapiro, 1990) suggest that both delayed or inaccurate diagnosis and the recurrence of breakdowns imply the lack of capacity and competence of the after-sales service department.

The previous studies (e.g., Raychaudhuri and Farooqi, 2013) imply that the capacity and competence of after-sales service department in the provision of services eventually

build-up among its service personnel (e.g., Raychaudhuri and Farooqi, 2013). An adequate supply of service personnel with sufficient knowledge, skills, attitudes and courteousness is a key for the effective provision of after-sales services (Atkinson, 2012; Cohen et al., 2006; Lervik et al., 2010; Mathe and Shapiro, 1990; Raychaudhuri and Farooqi, 2013). In this regard, previous studies (such as Boshoff and Mels 1995; Choudhary et al., 2011; Lervik et al., 2010) suggest that after-sales service personnel's competence to skilfully diagnose and reinstall the product is affected by proper documentation of previous repairs/modifications performed (Lervik et al., 2010), the guidelines and procedures of after-sales service provision (Choudhary et al., 2011) and the work environment of organisation including the behaviour of supervisors and team norms imposed by co-workers (Boshoff and Mels 1995).

Previous studies also provide evidence for the importance of professionalism and credibility of service provision (such as Alba and Hutchinson 1987; Brush and Artz, 1999; Dagger and Sweeney, 2007; Lewis and Entwistle, 1990). The degree of professionalism and the level of care demonstrated enhance credibility and trustworthiness of the service provider that the service will be delivered as agreed (Alba and Hutchinson 1987; Brush and Artz, 1999; Dagger and Sweeney, 2007) and the repaired product will conform with what has been promised, ultimately fulfilling customer expectations (Lewis and Entwistle, 1990).

Methodology

Sample and methods of data collection

Home appliances market of Sri Lanka is dominated by a wide range of world reputed brands (such as LG, Haier, Whirlpool, Samsung, Toshiba and Panasonic). The literature (e.g., Raychaudhuri and Farooqi, 2013) suggests that the competition between manufactures of world reputed brands led to the standardization of products reducing differences between product features offered to consumers. As a result, after-sales services have become a key

differentiator (Ramaswamy et al., 2002). Our experience in the Sri Lankan consumer market does not vary from the situation described in the literature reviewed above (such as Ramaswamy et al., 2002; Rigopoulou et al., 2008; Saccani et al., 2007; Shaharudin et al., 2009). A handful of Sri Lankan firms operate as sole-agents for different world reputed brands of home appliances. These sole-agents sell the products through their networks of branches and franchised agents island-wide. With regard to the provision of after-sales services, these sole-agents provide services either directly through their after-sales service departments or franchised agents.

Our study is confined to an after-sales service department of one of the large private sector firms operating in Sri Lanka, which was established in the early 1970s and currently holds an investment grade “A” from Fitch rating. The firm operates as the sole-agent for many world’s reputed brands in household electric and electronic appliances. It sells these appliances through a network of branches and franchised agents island-wide. This study is limited in its scope to investigate the direct provision of after-sales services at the site of after-sales service department of the sole-agent. We imposed this constraint since the literature (Low, 2013, p. 67) suggests that the provision of after-sales services by a lead firm will vary from direct supply, sub-contracting arrangements, agency relationships and franchising. With regard to the operation of after-sales service department, preliminary investigations revealed that customers’ first point of contact to receive after-sales service is the call centre. Relevant information is then passed from the call centre to appropriate after-sales service personnel. Thereafter, depending on the situation, a service technician is sent to the customer’s site. If it is difficult to provide a remedy at the customer’s site, the product is brought into the after-sales service department for repair or replacement.

After-sales service department of this firm is headed by a general manager; one senior engineer, 20 service engineers and 52 service technicians are the rest of the personnel

attached to the department by the time of data collection in the first quarter of 2014. Each service engineer and each service technician working under the supervision of service engineers are responsible for one particular product category to which he/she has been assigned to. The firm allowed us to access the entire study populations of 20 service engineers and 52 service technicians attached to the after-sales service department, and 91 customers who obtained services during the last 6 months by the time of the survey. Hence, we collected data covering the entire three study populations (populations = samples) during the first quarter of 2014. For the data collection, three self-administered questionnaires were developed and ensured anonymity of the respondents to reduce evaluation apprehension.

Measures

The questionnaire that targeted service engineers had 14 items covering aspects such as human resource availability, decision-making, communication, and material/parts management (refer to Table 1). The questionnaire that targeted service technicians had 11 items covering aspects such as their capabilities and training received (refer to Table 2). The questionnaire that targeted customers had 18 items covering aspects such as call centre operation and manner in which the situation was handled by the after-sales service department (refer to Table 3). We have designed these measures based on the insight gained from the literature reviewed above (such as Dagger and Sweeney, 2007; Raychaudhuri and Farooqi, 2013; Shaharudin et al., 2009) since we have not come across previous empirical studies that resemble our study. Responses to all the measures were on a five point Likert-scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Methods of data analysis

Principle component factor analysis was used as a form of data reduction. Descriptive statistics and plots were used to describe the data. When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of response bias and multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2006). Hence, recommended statistical tests were conducted to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias in our data (refer to Hair et al., 2006). In doing so, we tested the data for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, and (d) construct reliability.

Results and discussion

The responses of service engineers for the 14-item measure had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.893. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of four factors, which explained 79% (79.19) of the variance. The items, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 1. Factor 1 was labelled as "resources", Factor 2 as "departmental systems", Factor 3 as "material management" and Factor 4 as "delivery to customer". To understand the nature of distribution of these factors probability-probability plots (P-P plot) were created comparing the empirical cumulative distribution function of each factor with the standard normal distribution function. Figure 1 (a-d) shows P-P plot of the four factors, which are normally distributed along the fitted lines.

Take in Table 1

Take in Figure 1

Means and standard deviations of the item measures are shown in Table 2. Within the factor of resources, service technicians' knowledge to diagnose the status of product (Mean = 4.38, SD = .50) and their knowledge to identify parts to be used (Mean = 4.38, SD = .72) obtained the highest mean values. Within the factor of departmental systems, the maintenance of records of service provision (Mean = 4.25, SD = .57) obtained the highest mean value. Within the factor of material management, the minimization of occurrences of spare parts mismatch (Mean = 4.06, SD = .44) obtained the highest mean value. Finally, within the factor of delivery to customer, the delivery of repaired item to the customer within a specified timeframe (Mean = 4.5, SD = .52) obtained the highest mean value. Means obtained by all 14 items can be identified as high having mean values above 3.5 on a five point Likert-scale.

Take in Table 2

The responses of service technicians for the 11-item measure had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.856. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 68% (68.25) of the variance. The items, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 3. Factor 1 was labelled as "knowledge", Factor 2 as "skills and attitudes" and Factor 3 as "training and support". To understand the nature of distribution of these factors, probability-probability plots (P-P plot) were created comparing the empirical cumulative distribution function of each factor with the standard normal distribution function. Figure 2 (a-c) shows P-P plot of the three factors, which are normally distributed along the fitted lines.

Take in Table 3

Take in Figure 2

Means and standard deviations of the item measures are shown in Table 4. Within the factor of knowledge, service technicians' knowledge to solve the problem (Mean = 4.45, SD = .59) obtained the highest mean value. Within the factor of skills and attitudes, service technicians' capabilities to communicate the status of product (Mean = 4.54, SD = .64) obtained the highest mean value. Within the factor of training and support, the relevancy of training provision (Mean = 3.83, SD = .59) obtained the highest mean value. Means obtained by all 11 items can be identified as high having mean values above 3.5 on a five point Likert-scale except two items. These were the provision of support to learn new things (Mean = 3.32, SD = .37) and the existence of supportive work environment (Mean = 3.36, SD = .48).

Take in Table 4

The responses of customers for the 18-item measure had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.920. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 66% (66.52) of the variance. The items, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 5. Factor 1 was labelled as "demonstrated expertise", Factor 2 as "call centre" and Factor 3 as "warranty". To understand the nature of distribution of these factors, probability-probability plots (P-P plot) were created comparing the empirical cumulative distribution function of each factor with the standard normal distribution function. Figure 3 (a-c) shows P-P plot of the three factors, which are normally distributed along the fitted lines.

Take in Table 5

Take in Figure 3

Means and standard deviations of the item measures are shown in Table 6. Within the factor of demonstrated expertise, service department's capability to diagnose the problem without delay (Mean = 4.63, SD = .72) obtained the highest mean value. Within the factor of call centre, satisfaction with the operating hours of the call centre (Mean = 4.58, SD = .76) obtained the highest mean value. Within the factor of warranty, the reasonability of charging procedure (Mean = 4.65, SD = .71) obtained the highest mean value. Means obtained by all 18 items can be identified as high having mean values above 3.5 on a five point Likert-scale.

Take in Table 6

Conclusions and implications

Our study investigated different dimensions of the provision of after-sales services of home appliances from the perspective of service engineers, service technicians and customers. The findings of the study suggest that the views of service engineers support the views of service technicians and customers. In other words, service engineers identified the capabilities of service technicians as adequate to diagnose faults, identify parts to be replaced, and to perform the repair. Service technicians and customers verified this. In our sample, customers did not have any direct interaction with after-sales service personnel since the call centre performed the role of middleman. The findings suggested the satisfaction of customers with call centre personnel's handling of the situation. Since customers do not interact directly with after-sales service personnel the views of customers represent the firm's capacity to diagnose and remedy the situation concerned, for which in our case, customers stated their satisfaction.

As reviewed in the literature (such as Raychaudhuri and Farooqi, 2013), firm's capacity to provide after-sales services eventually build up among its after-sales service personnel. The existence of line of authority in making decisions, policy for after-sales service, communication channels between the immediate supervisor (i.e., service engineers) and subordinates (i.e., service technicians) as well as after-sales service department and customers through the call centre have assisted in providing timely service to customers.

The findings of the study have both theoretical and practical implications. With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, first, there is surprisingly little empirical research on the provision of after-sales services for consumers. It is even rare to find studies on the provision of after-sales services of home appliances, specifically in the context of developing countries where almost all products for sale are reputed brands imported from the developed world.

Second, the level of provision of a service can be evaluated in terms of self-evaluation, peer evaluation, supervisory evaluation and consumer evaluation (Behrman & Perreault, 1982). The present study investigated the perceptions of supervisor (i.e., service engineers) and subordinates (i.e., service technicians) on their provision of and customers on their experiences of receiving after-sales service. In this regard, on the one hand, the literature suggests (e.g. Steers and Porter, 1991) that employees' perception on what they deliver is a challenge because their perception drives their behaviour (e.g. Steers and Porter, 1991). Therefore, the literature emphasises (e.g., Mukherjee and Malhotra, 2006) the importance of evaluating employee perception on what they deliver (e.g., Mukherjee and Malhotra, 2006). On the other hand, consumers, both novice and longer-term, can provide valuable information of their experience on different aspects of the provision of after-sales services (Brush and Artz 1999). Therefore, it is important to obtain customer experiences of after-sales service provision. In this context, we operationalized different dimensions of the

provision of after-sales services from these three perspectives (service engineers, service technicians and customers) and used multiple parameters to evaluate the nature of provision. The measures we have used were empirically based and were shown to be valid and reliable. We have not come across previous studies that collected data from multiple sources that have slight resemblance to our study. For instance, previous studies such as Raychaudhuri and Farooqi (2013) and Shaharudin et al. (2009) used data provided by customers while Saccani et al. (2006) used data provided by managers. Hence, measures we have created could be utilised as a diagnostic tool for the better understanding of the provision of after-sales services from multiple perspectives. Practitioners could use the findings to analyse and assess issues in the provision of after-sales services to take necessary corrective actions to achieve success.

Third, according to Brush and Artz (1999), the outcomes of after-sales service provision reflect what is accomplished as a result of the service; customers can evaluate interaction, timeliness, and operation-related after-sales dimensions. Our findings identified warranty, service provider's capacity and competence to deliver the service, dependability and trust that the service will be delivered as agreed, call centre personnel's behaviour in inspiring confidence and giving a feeling of credibility, service reliability and trustworthiness, attention given to needs and feelings of the customer, adherence to timelines in delivering the repaired product/replacement to the customer, the installation of the product to its original status in a situation of a repair, and administrative procedures of the service provider as important dimensions of the provision of after-sales services. These dimensions are of importance to the organisation as well as to the customer.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the practice, first, the findings imply the importance of after-sales service departments having capacity and competence to provide the required service from the perspective of employees and customers. After-sales service

departments, in this regard, depend on their service personnel- their knowledge, skills, experience, the level of care and the overall degree of professionalism- in achieving desired outcomes. Service personnel's capability to diagnose faults, identify required spare parts, provide a remedy within a pre-defined timeframe avoiding recurrence were identified as important. We inquired about the provision of formal training opportunities for service technicians. According to Lervik et al. (2010, p. 291-294), in addition to formal training, service personnel can deepen their understanding of installed systems and general proficiency in problem solving through regular exposure to different kinds of problems. Further, informal learning through socialization with other after-sales service personnel help them to update and share knowledge and experience (Lervik et al., 2010). Therefore, future research could incorporate such variables to provide a broader understanding. However, service technicians identified the provision of support to learn new things and the existence of supportive work environment as lacking in the workplace, which imply the need of some attention. Second, call centre personnel's way of handling complaints and their interactions between after-sales service department and customers could be identified as having greater influence on the customers' evaluation of their experiences of after-sales service provision.

Overall, the provision of after-sales services has emerged as a source of competitive advantage in the home appliances market and it is very rare to find empirical studies that collected data with such a wide coverage in the literature. Therefore, we believe that the findings of our study provided some valuable information for decision makers in the home appliance sector and made a contribution to the literature by providing baseline data that would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

However, our sample is confined to an after-sales service department of one of the large private sector firms operating in Sri Lanka. Further, we designed our study based on self-report measures since we were not given access to secondary data by the firm. Although

we collected data from three different sources, multi-level analysis was beyond the scope of the study since the study was confined to a single firm. Yet, we covered the entire three study populations of service engineers, service technicians and customers that the firm allowed us access. Future researchers can use the measures we have proposed in this study to widen the scope of the investigation by covering specific industry or country contexts. The findings highlighted possible concerns over the provision of support to learn new things and the existence of supportive work environment for after-sales service personnel. In this regard, although the results of questionnaire survey provided access to the breadth of experience interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. Therefore, there is a need for further in-depth case studies for further understanding. The last but not least, future studies could include comparisons between the provision of after-sales services at the site of franchise agents and at the site customers to widen the scope of investigation.

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Tables and figures

Tables

Table 1: Factor analysis – perceptions of service engineers

	F1: Resources	F2: Departmental systems	F3: Material management	F4: Delivery to customer
My service technicians are knowledgeable to diagnose problems in products	.885			
My service technicians are knowledgeable to identify parts to be replaced	.849			
My service technicians have appropriate skills to perform the repair	.792			
My service technicians use recommended tools/equipment for the repair	.776			
Our department has a defined line of authority		.786		
Our department has a policy on after-sales service provision		.759		
We maintain records of after-sales service provision		.742		
We communicate relevant information to service technicians timely		.735		
We communicate relevant information to customers timely		.702		
We minimize occurrences of spare parts mismatch			.849	
Our department has parts movement monitoring system			.814	
We minimize parts storage distance			.779	
We deliver the repaired item to the customer within the pre-defined timeframe				.731
My service technicians complete the job within the pre-defined time frame				.714
Explained variation	38.98	22.21	10.04	7.96
Eigenvalue	3.85	1.71	1.41	1.11
Cronbach's alpha	.786	.739	.801	.722
AVE	.68	.55	.66	.52
Square root of AVE	.82	.74	.81	.72
Construct reliability	.90	.89	.85	.69

Table 2: Means and standard deviations - perceptions of service engineers

	Mean	SD
Resources:		
My service technicians are knowledgeable to diagnose problems in products	4.38	.50
My service technicians are knowledgeable to identify parts to be replaced	4.38	.72
My service technicians have appropriate skills to perform the repair	3.88	.62
My service technicians use recommended tools/equipment for the repair	3.69	.79
Overall	4.08	.51
Departmental systems:		
We maintain records of after-sales service provision	4.25	.57
We communicate relevant information to service technicians timely	4.13	.72
Our department has a policy on after-sales service provision	4.06	.77
We communicate relevant information to customers timely	4.00	.76
Our department has a defined line of authority	3.75	.86
Overall	4.03	.54
Material management:		
We minimize occurrences of spare parts mismatch	4.06	.44
Our department has parts movement monitoring system	3.81	.75
We minimize parts storage distance	3.56	.96
Overall	3.81	.57
Delivery to customer:		
We deliver the repaired item to the customer within the pre-defined timeframe	4.50	.52
My service technicians complete the job within the pre-defined time frame	3.88	.72
Overall	4.19	.57

Table 3: Factor analysis – perceptions of service technicians

	F1: Knowledge	F2: Skills and attitudes	F3: Training and support
I have knowledge to diagnose the problem	.807		
I have knowledge on how to solve the problem	.765		
I have knowledge to identify appropriate spare parts to be used	.735		
I have appreciable attitudes towards providing services		.826	
I have skills to solve the problem		.795	
I have capability to communicate the status of the product		.751	
The depth of training I received is adequate			.882
I have capability to understand the content of training provided			.823
Training programmes provided to me are relevant to after-sales service provision			.811
Our department maintains supportive work environment for us			.734
Our department provides support to learn new things			.711
Explained variation	29.432	25.308	13.510
Eigenvalue	2.649	2.278	1.216
Cronbach's alpha	.740	.721	.736
AVE	.59	.63	.61
Square root of AVE	.77	.79	.78
Construct reliability	.81	.83	.93

Table 4: Means and standard deviations - perceptions service technicians

Item	Mean	SD
Knowledge:		
I have knowledge on how to solve the problem	4.45	.59
I have knowledge to identify appropriate spare parts to be used	4.40	.49
I have knowledge to diagnose the problem	4.33	.69
Overall	4.39	.45
Skills and attitudes:		
I have capability to communicate the status of the product	4.54	.55
I have appreciable attitudes towards providing services	4.13	.60
I have skills to solve the problem	3.58	.63
Overall	4.08	.37
Training and support:		
Training programmes provided to me are relevant to after-sales service provision	3.83	.59
The depth of training I received is adequate	3.80	.56
I have capability to understand the content of training provided	3.69	.61
Our department maintains supportive work environment for us	3.36	.48
Our department provides support to learn new things	3.32	.37
Overall	3.62	.44

Table 5: Factor analysis – perceptions of customers

	F1: Demonstrated expertise	F2: Call centre	F3: Warranty
Competence shown by the after-sales service department during the job was appreciable	.870		
The way job was handled by the after-sales service department was trustworthy	.832		
Repaired/replacement product was delivered as promised	.829		
The problem diagnosed was correct	.813		
The product is in use/operation after the repair	.791		
Faults in the products were diagnosed without delay	.768		
Repair/replacement was completed as promised	.765		
Time taken for the repair was reasonable	.725		
Call centre personnel showed appreciable willingness to help me		.853	
Conflicts occurred between call centre personnel and myself were negligible		.804	
Call centre personnel were aware about my needs		.778	
Call centre personnel gave good attention to my complaint		.755	
Operating hours of the call centre is satisfactory		.754	
Call centre personnel recoded/documented my complaint correctly		.744	
After-sales service department responded to my complaint promptly		.710	
Warranty period provided for the product is sufficient			.872
Charging procedure of repair/replacement was reasonable			.810
Warranty terms provided for the product is satisfactory			.793
Explained variation	32.67	20.64	12.21
Eigenvalue	4.97	2.85	1.81
Cronbach's alpha	.821	.796	.721
AVE	.598	.614	.682
Square root of AVE	.773	.784	.826
Construct reliability	.962	.949	.865

Table 6: Means and standard deviations - perceptions of customers

	Mean	SD
Demonstrated expertise:		
Faults in the products were diagnosed without delay	4.63	.71
The product is in use/operation after the repair	4.62	.70
Repair/replacement was completed as promised	4.61	.71
Repaired/replacement product was delivered as promised	4.60	.75
The problem diagnosed was correct	4.59	.74
Competence shown by the after-sales service department during the job was appreciable	4.58	.79
Time taken for the repair was reasonable	4.57	.77
The way job was handled by the after-sales service department was trustworthy	4.53	.77
Overall	4.56	.72
Call centre:		
Operating hours of the call centre is satisfactory	4.58	.75
Call centre personnel gave good attention to my complaint	4.51	.72
Call centre personnel showed appreciable willingness to help me	4.49	.79
Call centre personnel were aware about my needs	4.46	.86
After-sales service department responded to my complaint promptly	4.43	.81
Conflicts occurred between call centre personnel and myself were negligible	4.31	.98
Call centre personnel recoded/documented my complaint correctly	3.94	.96
Overall	4.36	.74
Warranty:		
Charging procedure of repair/replacement was reasonable	4.65	.71
Warranty period provided for the product is sufficient	4.64	.69
Warranty terms provided for the product is satisfactory	4.41	.85
Overall	4.55	.71

Figures

(a) Resources

(b) Departmental systems

(c) Material management

(d) Delivery to customer

Figure 1: P-P Plot of perceptions of service engineers

(a) Knowledge

(b) Skills and attitudes

(c) Training and support

Figure 2: P-P Plot of perceptions of service personnel

(a) Demonstrated expertise

(b) Call centre

(c) Warranty

Figure 3: P-P Plot of perceptions of customers